

INITIATION OF FREE-EDGE DELAMINATION IN A COMPOSITE LAMINATE UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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SUMMARY: This paper is concerned with the onset of free-edge delamination in composite laminates subjected to fatigue loading. The material system investigated was a carbon fiber-reinforced toughened bismaleimide (IM7/5250-4). A quasi-isotropic laminate with a $[90_2/\pm 30]_s$ lay-up was employed and the onset of free-edge delamination determined under static loading and compression-compression fatigue loading. The interlaminar stresses in the free-edge region were calculated using an analytical model, taking into consideration residual curing stresses. The stress for the onset of delamination under static compression and the cycles for the onset of delamination under fatigue loading at various fatigue stress levels were experimentally determined. Delamination occurred at the 30/-30 interface for all specimens under both static and fatigue loadings. The critical component of the interlaminar stresses was found to be the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} at the 30/-30 interface due to mechanical loading and curing residual stresses. This stress τ_{xz} was therefore used to predict the onset of delamination in conjunction with the S-N relationship for in-plane shear, which was obtained from the fatigue testing of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ specimens. The experimental data for both static and fatigue loadings compare well with the analytical prediction.

KEYWORDS: delamination onset, interlaminar shear stress, fatigue, bismaleimide.

INTRODUCTION

Free-edge delamination of composite laminates under in-plane static loading has been extensively studied since the early 1970's [1-5]. From the results of these studies, for example [2, 4, 5], the nature of the interlaminar stress components is well understood and the onset of delamination under static loading is reasonably well predicted. However, little work has been reported on the onset of delamination under fatigue loading. The objective of this study was to develop the capability to predict the onset of free-edge delamination in composite laminates subjected to fatigue loading. The material system investigated was a carbon fiber-reinforced toughened bismaleimide (IM7/5250-4). A quasi-isotropic laminate with a $[90_2/\pm 30]_s$ lay-up was employed and the onset of delamination determined under compression-compression fatigue loading. Applied compressive loading was chosen, to eliminate the interaction of transverse cracks which usually occurs prior to delamination under applied tension. A laminate was designed to produce an interlaminar normal tensile stress under applied uniaxial compression. When this laminate is subjected to an axial compressive stress, delamination occurs due to interlaminar stresses in the free-edge region prior to the formation of transverse cracks. The interlaminar stresses at the free-edge region were calculated using an analytical model [4], taking into consideration curing residual stresses. The maximum-stress failure theory was applied to predict the initiation of

delamination. Because of the presence of a severe stress gradient along the free edge of the specimen, the concept of an effective stress, the average stress over a distance from the free edge equivalent to the thickness of one ply, was utilized. The thermomechanical properties required for the analytical calculations were determined experimentally in a complementary study. The stress-free temperature was also determined from the deflection of an unsymmetric laminate strip as a function of temperature to calculate the residual interlaminar stresses due to curing. The stress for the onset of delamination under static compression and the cycles for the onset of delamination under fatigue loading at various fatigue stress levels were experimentally determined. Acoustic emission was employed to detect the onset of delamination, and the result was confirmed visually using a microscope. Delamination occurred at the 30/-30 interface for all specimens under both static and fatigue loadings. The critical component of the interlaminar stresses was found to be the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} at the 30/-30 interface due to mechanical loading and curing residual stresses. This stress, τ_{xz} , was therefore used to predict the onset of delamination in conjunction with the S-N relation for in-plane shear which was obtained from fatigue testing of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ specimens. The experimental data for both static and fatigue loadings compare well with analytical predictions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The material system selected for this study was a graphite/bismaleimide, IM7/5250-4, obtained in the form of unidirectional prepreg tape. A laminate with a stacking sequence of $[90_2/\pm 30]_s$ was fabricated according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle and postcured at 227°C for five hours. The panel was cut into rectangular specimens 15 cm long and 2 cm wide using a diamond-impregnated saw blade. Glass/epoxy end-tabs, 5 cm long, were bonded at each end leaving a gage section of 5 cm, and the specimen edges were polished to enhance microscopic detection of delamination. Unidirectional laminates were also fabricated to determine the necessary thermoelastic properties for calculation of the interlaminar stresses in the free-edge region and to measure the appropriate strengths required for the prediction of the onset of delamination. The average fiber content was determined to be 64 percent by volume. The Poisson's ratio ν_{yz} was determined from the tensile loading of a $[90]_{16T}$ specimen with strains measured in y- and z-directions and utilized to calculate G_{yz} .

A device was designed and built to provide side support to the specimen and thereby prevent premature failure due to specimen buckling under compressive load. This side support has a central opening to accommodate an acoustic emission transducer to detect the onset of delamination under static as well as fatigue loading. An acoustic emission transducer was mounted on the flat face of the specimen using high-temperature vacuum grease to monitor the onset of delamination. A brittle white coating was applied to one of the free edges for the visual observation of the onset of delamination during loading. At the first indication of delamination, the specimen was unloaded and the delamination confirmed by microscopic examination of the specimen edge.

Of all the interlaminar stress components, the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} , was found to be responsible for the free-edge delamination under applied compressive loading. Therefore, to predict the onset of delamination under fatigue loading, an S-N curve must be generated for interlaminar shear loading. Fatigue strength for in-plane shear loading was assumed to be equivalent to fatigue strength for interlaminar shear loading, and fatigue life data were generated from the uniaxial tension-tension fatigue of the $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ specimens. Five stress levels were chosen with a minimum of five replicates at each stress level. All specimens were

fatigued to final failure on an MTS test machine in the displacement-control mode. The fatigue tests were conducted at a frequency of 10 Hz and a stress ratio of $R= 0.1$.

Fatigue life data were reduced by employing a statistical procedure which allows the generation of S-N curves with some statistical value without resorting to an extremely large data base. The details of this procedure can be found in [6]. The outline of this procedure is as follows:

- (a) The fatigue life data at each stress level are fitted to a two-parameter Weibull distribution

$$X(n) = \exp[-(n/N)^a] \quad (1)$$

where a is the shape parameter and N is the scale parameter (characteristic fatigue life). These parameters are estimated using a maximum-likelihood method.

- (b) All the fatigue life data for each stress level are normalized with respect to the characteristic life estimated in step (a). Then the common shape parameter is determined by pooling the normalized data for all stress levels, and the characteristic life for each stress level is re-estimated using the common shape parameter.

- (c) The estimated characteristic lives are fitted to a classical power law of the S-N relationship

$$S(n) = aN^b \quad (2)$$

where a and b are material constants which are determined by least-square regression analysis. N is the characteristic fatigue life estimated in step (b).

The fatigue cycles at the onset of delamination were determined under compression-compression fatigue with a frequency of 5 Hz and $R= 1$, using a $[90_2/\pm 30]_S$ specimen with the same dimensions as those used in the static tests. Specimens were fatigued until the onset of delamination and unloaded to confirm the delamination under a microscope. A total of 12 specimens were tested at six different stress levels with 1 to 3 replicates at each stress level. The location of the interface where delamination occurred was identified for each specimen under a microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The thermomechanical properties of the material system determined for calculation of interlaminar stresses and prediction of the onset of free-edge delamination are listed in Table 1.

Interlaminar Stresses in the Free-Edge Region

Interlaminar stresses at each interface in the free-edge region were calculated using the variational model developed by Pagano [4]. The distribution of interlaminar stresses, σ_z , τ_{yz} , and τ_{xz} , at the 30/-30 interface and the midplane due to an applied compression of 1 MPa and due to thermal loading alone (from curing residual stresses) are shown in Figures 1-4. There is only an interlaminar normal tensile stress present at the midplane under either mechanical loading or thermal loading due to curing residual stresses. All three interlaminar stress components exist at the 30/-30 interface. Interlaminar stresses at the other ply interfaces were

found to be insignificant compared to those at the midplane and the 30/-30 interface. There is a large gradient in the interlaminar stress components in the vicinity of the free edge. At both the midplane and the 30/-30 interface, the interlaminar normal stress is tensile due to mechanical loading, whereas it is compressive due to residual curing stresses. This compressive interlaminar normal stress increases the applied stress for the onset of delamination at these interfaces. A large interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} exists at the 30/-30 interface and is negative for both applied mechanical loading and curing residual stresses.

Table 1: Thermomechanical properties of IM7/5250-4 under ambient conditions

Longitudinal modulus, E_x , GPa	165
Transverse modulus, $E_y=E_z$, GPa	10.3
Shear modulus, $G_{xy}=G_{xz}$, GPa	5.8
Transverse shear modulus, G_{yz} , GPa	3.3
Major Poisson's ratio, $\nu_{xy}=\nu_{xz}$	0.31
Minor Poisson's ratio, ν_{yz}	0.56
Coefficient of thermal expansion	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
Longitudinal, α_x	0.45
Transverse, $\alpha_y=\alpha_z$	24.7
Stress-free temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	177
Fiber volume, V_f , %	64
Cured ply thickness, mm	0.127
Shear strength, MPa	122
Transverse strength, MPa	61.3

The subscript x refers to the fiber direction and y and z refer to directions perpendicular to the fiber direction.

Fig. 1: Interlaminar normal stress distribution at the midplane due to applied compression

Fig. 2: Interlaminar stress distributions at the 30/-30 interface due to applied compression

Fig. 3: Interlaminar normal stress distribution at the midplane due to curing residual stress

Fig. 4: Interlaminar stress distributions at the 30/-30 interface due to curing residual stress

Prediction of the Onset of Delamination Under Static Loading

The results of the interlaminar stress analysis were applied to the prediction of the onset of delamination in conjunction with a failure theory [7]. The average value of each stress component at the free edge, instead of the maximum value, was assumed to be the effective stress level, i.e. that stress which is responsible for failure. The effective stress is obtained by averaging the interlaminar stress components over a fixed distance h_0 from the free edge along the width of the laminate at the interface in question and is given by

$$\bar{\sigma}_I(z) = \frac{1}{h_0} \int_0^{h_0} \sigma_I(y,z) dy \quad (3)$$

The fixed distance h_0 was taken as a thickness of one ply in all cases.

For prediction of the stress level at the onset of delamination and its location (interface), the maximum stress criterion was applied. Failure via delamination was assumed to occur when any of the effective stresses, $\bar{\sigma}_I(z)$, at each interface first reached the corresponding strength. By comparison of all interlaminar stresses with the corresponding strengths at the 30/-30 interface and the midplane for the laminate used in this study, the critical effective stress component was found to be the interlaminar shear stress, τ_{xz} , at the 30/-30 interface. Thus, the onset of delamination was predicted when this effective stress reached the interlaminar shear strength. The interlaminar shear strength of the laminate was assumed to be equal to the in-plane shear strength of the material system. Results from [8] demonstrate that the difference between the interlaminar shear strength and in-plane shear strength is less than two percent for the graphite/epoxy AS4/3501-6 composite system.

The predicted stress for the onset of delamination compares fairly well with the experimental value as shown in Table 2. The experimental value is an average of four specimens with a coefficient of variation, (C_v), of 4.5 percent.

Table 2: Comparison of prediction and experiment for onset of delamination under static loading

	Onset stress, MPa		Delaminated interface	
	Prediction	Experiment	Prediction	Experiment
$[90_2/\pm 30]_s$	346	312	30/-30	30/-30
$C_v, \%$	-	4.5	-	-

Delamination occurred at the 30/-30 interfaces for all specimens, as shown in Figure 5. The exact location of the delamination with respect to the ply interface could also be identified from these micrographs. No transverse crack was found to occur prior to delamination.

Fig. 5: Micrograph showing the onset of delamination for the $[90_2/\pm 30]_s$ specimen

This is consistent with the analytical prediction of the stress to first-ply failure being greater than the stress for the onset of delamination under these conditions.

Onset of Delamination Under Fatigue Loading

Since τ_{xz} is responsible for the free-edge delamination, the inplane shear S-N relationship and the calculated τ_{xz} under a given load (including curing residual stress) were utilized to predict the onset of delamination under fatigue loading. Fatigue failure was assumed to occur when the fatigue interlaminar shear stress, τ_{xz} , reached the fatigue shear strength of the material system. Figure 6 shows the shear S-N relationship determined under tension-tension fatigue from the $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminate.

Fig. 6: S-N relationship for shear and fatigue data of $[90_2/\pm 30]_s$ laminates in terms of the calculated effective stress τ_{xz} at the 30/-30 interface. Solid line: shear S-N relation from $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminate; open circle: fatigue data from $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminate; and solid circle: fatigue data from $[90_2/\pm 30]_s$ laminate

The open circles are the fatigue data obtained from experiment, and the solid line represents the regression line which was fitted to Eqn 2 using the data reduction scheme described previously. The material constants a and b in Eqn 2 determined from the regression analysis are 135.7 and -0.065, respectively. For a given interlaminar shear stress the number of cycles for the onset of delamination can then be predicted from Eqn 2. The interlaminar shear stress generated in the fatigue loading of any laminate can be calculated using the global-local model. The fatigue data at the onset of delamination for the $[90_2/\pm 30]_s$ specimen under compression-compression fatigue are plotted (solid circle) in Figure 6. The shear stresses in the ordinate are obtained from the applied fatigue stress on the $[90_2/\pm 30]_s$ laminate using the global-local model. The experimental data appear to fit the predicted S-N relation reasonably well with a little higher trend. This higher trend may be partially attributed to the difficulty in determining the exact number of cycles for the onset of delamination under cyclic loading. It may also be due to the inability of the acoustic emission system to capture a very small signal from the initiation of delamination. Further work is needed to refine the technique.

CONCLUSIONS

An investigation was conducted to determine the initiation of free-edge delamination in IM7/5250-4 graphite/epoxy laminates under static and fatigue loading. Predictions regarding stress level and location (interface) for the onset of delamination agree very well with experimental results under static loading. The approach used in this work appears to be promising for prediction of onset of delamination under fatigue loading. In both static and fatigue loading no transverse ply failure was observed prior to free-edge delamination for this laminate. The absence of any damage prior to delamination might be helpful for prediction of

the delamination. The onset of delamination in this laminate can be accurately determined experimentally by monitoring strains in the axial and thickness directions and the use of acoustic emission. Further study is required to obtain confidence in this approach using a variety of laminates and different loading conditions.

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